

File
Align
CP35, seeds:
Group 1, MtrunA17_Chr1g0203181, alternative source
roots (5), roots ribo-minus (19)

Save

Consensus
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

Identity

1. 5.912675575_SRR3997853.28764822
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

2. 19.2753523761_SRR949259.54829487
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

3. MtrunA17_Chr1g0203181 cDNA
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

Home
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Full Screen

File
Align

CP35, seeds:
Group 2, MtrunA17_Chr4g0008361, alternative source
seedlings (7, 15, 16), shoot apical buds (11)

Save

✉ 📄

- Consensus
- Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
- Identity
- 1. 7 36261719_SRR10058818.6525457
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
 - 2. 11 226828654_SRR11637998.32044744
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
 - 3. 15 312435847_SRR11637999.33145531
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
 - 4. 16 290153851_SRR11637999.10863535
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
 - 5. MtrunA17_Chr4g0008361 cDNA
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

950 960 970 980 990 1,000 1,010 1,020 1,030 1,040 1,050 1,058 1,070 1,080 1,094 1,100 1,110 1,120 1,130 1,140 1,150 1,160

:T R A H S A N V G F Q E Y D V C C R P * T R T I P H C I S H L Q R Q N E H * R S * * T N D Q C S E Q E I --G R A S C R --- E R V * /SN/I ? L /VV /FA /VI /V F H Q Q
 V P E L T Q Q M W D S K N M M C A A D P R H G R Y L T A S A I F R G K M S T K E V D E Q M I N V Q N K R S --E E R R V ---G K E C ? ? ? W /CS /L ? Y S T N R
 Y Q S S L S K C G I P R I * C V L P T L D T D D T S L H Q P S S E A K * A L K K L M N K * S M F R T R D R -- K S V V * ---G K S V ? ? ? G /VR /C ? I P P T Q

C C T A G A C A O G G A C G A T A C C T C A C T G C A T C A G C C A T C T T C A G A G G C A A A A T G A G C A C T A A A A G A A G T G A T G A A C A A A T G A T C A A T G T C A G A A C A A G A G A T O G --G A A G A G C G T G T C T A G ---G G A A A G A G T G T A G A T C T G G T G G T G C C G T A T
 * T R T I P H C I S H L Q R Q N E H * R S * * T N D Q C S E Q E I --G R A S C R --- E R V * I S V V A V
 P R H G R Y L T A S A I F R G K M S T K E V D E Q M I N V Q N K R S --E E R R V ---G K E C R S R W S P Y
 L D T D D T S L H Q P S S E A K * A L K K L M N K * S M F R T R D R -- K S V V * ---G K S V D L G G R R

C T C A C T C A G C A A A T C T G G G A T C C A A G A A T A T G A T G T C C T G C C G A C C C T A G A C A O G G A C G A T A C C T C A C T G C A T C A G C C A T C T T C A G A G G C A A A A T G A G C A C T A A A A G A A G T G A T G A A C A A A T G A T C A A T G T C A G A A C A A G A G A T O G --G A A G A G C G T G T C T A G ---G G A A A G A G T G

H S A N V G F Q E Y D V C C R P * T R T I P H C I S H L Q R Q N E H * R S * * T N D Q C S E Q E I
 L T Q Q M W D S K N M M C A A D P R H G R Y L T A S A I F R G K M S T K E V D E Q M I N V Q N K R S
 S L S K C G I P R I * C V L P T L D T D D T S L H Q P S S E A K * A L K K L M N K * S M F R T R D

G A A T A G A T G T G T C C T G C C G A C C C T A G A C A O G G A C G A T A C C T C A C T G C A T C A G C C A T C T T C A G A G G C A A A A T G A G C A C T A A A A G A A G T G A T G A A C A A A T G A T C A A T G T C A G A A C A A G A G A T O G --G A A G A G C G T G T C T A G ---G G A A A G A G T G

E Y D V C C R P * T R T I P H C I S H L Q R Q N E H * R S * * T N D Q C S E Q E I --G R A S C R --- E R V
 N M M C A A D P R H G R Y L T A S A I F R G K M S T K E V D E Q M I N V Q N K R S --E E R R V ---G K E
 I * C V L P T L D T D D T S L H Q P S S E A K * A L K K L M N K * S M F R T R D R -- K S V V * ---G K S

C C A A A T C T G G G A T C C A A G A A T A T G A T G T C C T G C C G A C C C T A G A C A O G G A C G A T A C C T C A C T G C A T C A G C C A T C T T C A G A G G C A A A A T G A G C A C T A A A A G A A G T G A T G A A C A A A T G A T C A A T G T C A G A A C A A G A G A T O G --G A A G A G C G T G T C T A G ---G G A A A G A G T G

A N V G F Q E Y D V C C R P * T R T I P H C I S H L Q R Q N E H * R S * * T N D Q C S E Q E I --G R A
 Q M W D S K N M M C A A D P R H G R Y L T A S A I F R G K M S T K E V D E Q M I N V Q N K R S --E E
 K C G I P R I * C V L P T L D T D D T S L H Q P S S E A K * A L K K L M N K * S M F R T R D R -- K S

:T R A H S A N V G F Q E Y D V C C R P * T R T I P H C I S H L Q R Q N E H * R S * * T N D Q C S E Q E I L I L L R R M D S K Q C Q I N C L * Y S T N R
 V P E L T Q Q M W D S K N M M C A A D P R H G R Y L T A S A I F R G K M S T K E V D E Q M I N V Q N K R S S Y F V E W I P N N V K S T V C D I P P T Q
 Y Q S S L S K C G I P R I * C V L P T L D T D D T S L H Q P S S E A K * A L K K L M N K * S M F R T R T H P T S S N G F Q T M S N Q L F V I F H Q Q

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%

CP35, seeds:

Group 3, MtrunA17_Chr4g0008401, alternative source

roots (1, 2, 3, 4), petioles (9, 12, 18), seedlings (13, 14), shoot apical buds (6), roots ribo-minus (17)

1,080 1,090 1,100 1,110 1,120 1,130 1,140 1,150 1,160 1,170 1,180 1,190 1,195 1,200 1,210 1,220 1,231 1,240 1,250 1,260 1,270 1,280 1,290 1,300 1,310

Consensus
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

Identity

- 1. 1 896040101_SRR3997853.12129348
- 2. 2 910407172_SRR3997853.26496419
- 3. 3 904658674_SRR3997853.20747921
- 4. 4 912752137_SRR3997853.28841384
- 5. 6 248093401_SRR11637999.12410145
- 6. 9 591567193_SRR15439239.10376508
- 7. 12 558258310_SRR15439238.18982977
- 8. 13 35657900_SRR10058818.5921638
- 9. 14 31109881_SRR10058818.1373619
- 10. 17 2505263617_SRR949257.27993806
- 11. 18 564232740_SRR15439238.3999731
- 12. MtrunA17_Chr4g0008401 cDNA

The image displays a nucleotide alignment viewer interface. At the top, a consensus sequence is shown with positions 1,080 to 1,310. Below it, several sequence frames (Frame 1, Frame 2, Frame 3) are visible. A list of 12 entries is on the left, each with a blue arrow pointing to a corresponding alignment. The alignments consist of nucleotide sequences with colored highlights (green, red, blue) indicating specific regions. Above the sequences are green bars representing sequence identity. At the bottom, a blue arrow indicates the reading frame for a protein translation, with a pink arrow pointing to a specific position.

CP35, seeds:
Group 4, MtrunA17_Chr7g0255791, alternative source
seedlings (8), shoot apical buds (10)

- Consensus
- Frame 1
- Frame 2
- Frame 3
- Identity
- FWD 1. 8 10357760_SRR10058814.2595568
- Frame 1
- Frame 2
- Frame 3
- REV 2. 10 213178767_SRR11637998.18394857
- Frame 1
- Frame 2
- Frame 3
- FWD 3. MtrunA17_Chr7g0255791 cDNA
- Frame 1
- Frame 2
- Frame 3

The alignment visualization shows a consensus sequence at the top with positions 1,090 to 1,310. Below it are three frames of sequence alignment. A green bar indicates the identity of the sequences. A cyan arrow points to a specific region in the third frame, likely representing a feature or seedling. The alignment includes various symbols like asterisks and question marks to denote matches and mismatches.

CP54, 14-dpi nodules, buds, seeds:

Overview, MtrunA17_Chr3g0105981, primary source

shoot apical buds (1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 11, 14, 15, 16, 20, 21, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 32, 34, 35, 36, [37], 38, 39, 40, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 51, 52, 53, 54, 55, 58, 68), 10-dpi nodules ([9], 10, [56], 57, 59, 60, 62, 63, 66, [67]), 14-dpi nodules (9, [10], 17, 19, [54], 61, 64, 65), petioles ([2], 8, 13, [24], [25], [26], 31, 33, 41, [43], 50), seedlings (7, 12, 18), shoots (3, 37, [40]), whole seedlings (56, [66], 67), leaves (22)

- ▶ FID 2. 55 302980074_SRR11637999.23689758
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
- ▶ FID 3. 1 186841254_SRR11637998.32956690
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
- ▶ REV 4. 2 138384731_SRR11637997.23070240
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
- ▶ REV 5. 3 755393679_SRR18944067.4401224
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
- ▶ REV 6. 4 317892599_SRR11637999.38602283
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
- ▶ FID 7. 5 186842903_SRR11637998.32958339
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
- ▶ REV 8. 6 121980897_SRR11637997.6666406
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
- ▶ REV 9. 7 46277764_SRR10058822.2329624
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
- ▶ REV 10. 11 167960837_SRR11637998.14076273
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
- ▶ FID 11. 12 43729605_SRR10058818.13993343
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
- ▶ REV 12. 14 254070798_SRR11637999.18387542
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
- ▶ FID 13. 15 163710058_SRR11637998.9825494
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
- ▶ FID 14. 16 97412111_SRR11637997.20667693
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
- ▶ REV 15. 18 24987456_SRR10058818.9463072
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

The image displays a multiple sequence alignment of nucleotide sequences. The sequences are arranged in rows, with a central reference sequence highlighted in green. Gaps in the sequences are indicated by asterisks (*). The alignment is color-coded to show conserved regions and gaps. The sequences are aligned to a common reference sequence, which is highlighted in green. The alignment shows high conservation across the sequences, with some gaps indicated by asterisks (*). The sequences are arranged in rows, with a central reference sequence highlighted in green. Gaps in the sequences are indicated by asterisks (*). The alignment is color-coded to show conserved regions and gaps. The sequences are aligned to a common reference sequence, which is highlighted in green. The alignment shows high conservation across the sequences, with some gaps indicated by asterisks (*).

CP54, 14-dpi nodules, buds, seeds: Part 1, MtrunA17_Chr3g0105981, primary source

Extract R.C. Translate Add Annotation Allow Editing Annotate & Predict Primer Design Save

Consensus
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

Identity

FID 1. MtrunA17_Chr3g0105981 cDNA
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

FID 2. 55 302980074_SRR11637999.23689758
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

FID 3. 1 186841254_SRR11637998.32956690
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 4. 2 138384731_SRR11637997.23070240
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 5. 3 755393679_SRR18944067.4401224
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 6. 4 317892599_SRR11637999.38602283
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

FID 7. 5 186842903_SRR11637998.32958339
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 8. 6 121980897_SRR11637997.6666406
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 9. 7 46277764_SRR10058822.2329624
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 10. 11 167960837_SRR11637998.14076273
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

FID 11. 12 43729605_SRR10058818.13993343
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 12. 14 254070798_SRR11637999.18387542
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

FID 13. 15 163710058_SRR11637998.9825494
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

FID 14. 16 97412111_SRR11637997.20667693
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 15. 18 24987456_SRR10058818.9463072
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

CP54, 14-dpi nodules, buds, seeds: Part 3, MtrunA17_Chr3g0105981, primary source

Extract R.C. Translate Add Annotation Allow Editing Annotate & Predict Primer Design Save

Consensus
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

Identity

REV 30. 59 1360699289_SRR5740870.30686042
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 31. 60 1177800158_SRR5740864.16162418
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 32. 62 1377417386_SRR5740870.12238054
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 33. 63 1165412635_SRR5740864.3774895
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 34. 64 1108039999_SRR5740862.17992999
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 35. 65 1071829601_SRR5740862.23155228
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

FIND 36. 66 1355858969_SRR5740870.25845722
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 37. 67 785847377_SRR2060975.6412147
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 38. 68 202070482_SRR11637998.7286572
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 39. 56 798957400_SRR2060975.7843299
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 40. 28 267394982_SRR11637999.31711726
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

FIND 41. 34 203638431_SRR11637998.8854521
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

FIND 42. 35 164224046_SRR11637998.10339482
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 43. 17 1116626002_SRR5740862.26579002
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 44. 8 584777219_SRR15439239.3586534
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 45. 23 88926218_SRR11637997.12181800
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

FIND 46. 29 194810346_SRR11637998.26436
 Frame 1

1,360 1,370 1,380 1,390 1,400 1,410 1,420 1,430 1,440 1,450 1,460 1,470 1,480 1,490 1,500 1,510 1,520 1,530 1,540 1,550 1,560 1,570 1,580 1,590 1,600 1,610

ACGGCACTATCTGGGCGGATCTGCTGTAACACACACATGGCCGCAATAAATACATATGCGTTTAAATAGTTATATCAGGAGCATGATCAGAAAGCTGAAACCTGGCGATTTGGGGGGCTTGGGATTAATCACAACCTGTTGATCCGTCAGATGATCCGTCAGGTTCCGATGGAG
 L H Y L L V D L A L T S H G L U V I Y H M L L I V I R S M I R H L K V A T L G G L D * S Q L L I R Q M I V A G F R L R F T L L M * H F T T G C U V F S V G * F Y * * Q S S W H
 R C T I F W W I L L * H M A * * Y I I C F * * L L S G A * S E S * K L R L W G A W I N H H C * S V R * S L Q V S D * D S H F * C R T L Q G V * F S V V D F T S N H P L G I
 T A L S S G G S C P N I T W P S N I S Y A F N S Y Y Q E H D Q K A E S C D F G G L G L I T T V D P S D D R C R F P I E I H T S N V E L Y R V C S F Q W L I L L V T I L L A S

G G S C P N I T W P S N I S Y A F N S Y Y Q E H D Q K A E S C D F G G L G L I T T V D P S D D R C R

GCTGAAACTTGGCAGCTTTGGGGGGCTTGGGATTAATCACAACCTGTTGATCCGTCAGATGATCCGTCAGGTTCCGATGGAG
 Q E H D Q K A E S C D F G G L G L I T T V D P S D D R C R F P I E
 R S M I R H L K V A T L G G L D * S Q L L I R Q M I V A G F R L R
 S G A * S E S * K L R L W G A W I N H H C * S V R * S L Q V S D *

GCTGAAACTTGGCAGCTTTGGGGGGCTTGGGATTAATCACAACCTGTTGATCCGTCAGATGATCCGTCAGGTTCCGATGGAG
 Q E H D Q K A E S C D F G G L G L I T T V D P S D D R C R F P I E
 R S M I R H L K V A T L G G L D * S Q L L I R Q M I V A G F R L R
 G A * S E S * K L R L W G A W I N H H C * S V R * S L Q V S D *

GCTGAAACTTGGCAGCTTTGGGGGGCTTGGGATTAATCACAACCTGTTGATCCGTCAGATGATCCGTCAGGTTCCGATGGAG
 H D Q K A E S C D F G G L G L I T T V D P S D D R C R F P I E I H
 M I R H L K V A T L G G L D * S Q L L I R Q M I V A G F R L R F
 A * S E S * K L R L W G A W I N H H C * S V R * S L Q V S D * D S

GCTGAAACTTGGCAGCTTTGGGGGGCTTGGGATTAATCACAACCTGTTGATCCGTCAGATGATCCGTCAGGTTCCGATGGAG
 Q E H D Q K A E S C D F G G L G L I T T V D P S D D R C R F P I
 I R S M I R H L K V A T L G G L D * S Q L L I R Q M I V A G F R L
 S G A * S E S * K L R L W G A W I N H H C * S V R * S L Q V S D *

GCTGAAACTTGGCAGCTTTGGGGGGCTTGGGATTAATCACAACCTGTTGATCCGTCAGATGATCCGTCAGGTTCCGATGGAG
 E H D Q K A E S C D F G G L G L I T T V D P S D D R C R F P I E
 S M I R H L K V A T L G G L D * S Q L L I R Q M I V A G F R L R
 G A * S E S * K L R L W G A W I N H H C * S V R * S L Q V S D * D

GCTGAAACTTGGCAGCTTTGGGGGGCTTGGGATTAATCACAACCTGTTGATCCGTCAGATGATCCGTCAGGTTCCGATGGAG
 E H D Q K A E S C D F G G L G L I T T V D P S D D R C R F P I E
 S M I R H L K V A T L G G L D * S Q L L I R Q M I V A G F R L R F
 A * S E S * K L R L W G A W I N H H C * S V R * S L Q V S D * D S

GCTGAAACTTGGCAGCTTTGGGGGGCTTGGGATTAATCACAACCTGTTGATCCGTCAGATGATCCGTCAGGTTCCGATGGAG
 H D Q K A E S C D F G G L G L I T T V D P S D D R C R F P I E I
 S M I R H L K V A T L G G L D * S Q L L I R Q M I V A G F R L R F
 A * S E S * K L R L W G A W I N H H C * S V R * S L Q V S D * D S

GCTGAAACTTGGCAGCTTTGGGGGGCTTGGGATTAATCACAACCTGTTGATCCGTCAGATGATCCGTCAGGTTCCGATGGAG
 V A L D A T S H R L V I R H M L L I V I R S M I R H L K V A T L G G L D * S Q L L I R Q M I V A
 W L L M Q L R H I A * * Y I I C F * * L L S G A * S E S * K L R L W G A W I N H H C * S V R * S L Q
 G G S * C N F T S P S N T S Y A F N S Y Y Q E H D Q K A E S C D F G G L G L I T T V D P S D D R C R

GCTGAAACTTGGCAGCTTTGGGGGGCTTGGGATTAATCACAACCTGTTGATCCGTCAGATGATCCGTCAGGTTCCGATGGAG
 Y Y Q E H D Q K A E S C D F G G L G L I T T V D P S D D R C R F P
 I I R S M I R H L K V A T L G G L D * S Q L L I R Q M I V A G F
 L L S G A * S E S * K L R L W G A W I N H H C * S V R * S L Q V S

GCTGAAACTTGGCAGCTTTGGGGGGCTTGGGATTAATCACAACCTGTTGATCCGTCAGATGATCCGTCAGGTTCCGATGGAG
 S Y Y Q E H D Q K A E S C D F G G L G L I T T V D P S D D R C R F P I E I H T S N V E L Y R V C S F
 V I R S M I R H L K V A T L G G L D * S Q L L I R Q M I V A G F R L R F T L L M * H F T T G C U V F
 L L S G A * S E S * K L R L W G A W I N H H C * S V R * S L Q V S D * D S H F * C R T L Q G V * F

GCTGAAACTTGGCAGCTTTGGGGGGCTTGGGATTAATCACAACCTGTTGATCCGTCAGATGATCCGTCAGGTTCCGATGGAG
 Y Y Q E H D Q K A E S C D F G G L G L I T T V D P S D D R C R F P I E I H T S N V E L Y R V C S F
 V I R S M I R H L K V A T L G G L D * S Q L L I R Q M I V A G F R L R F T L L M * H F T T G C U V F
 L L S G A * S E S * K L R L W G A W I N H H C * S V R * S L Q V S D * D S H F * C R T L Q G V * F

GCTGAAACTTGGCAGCTTTGGGGGGCTTGGGATTAATCACAACCTGTTGATCCGTCAGATGATCCGTCAGGTTCCGATGGAG
 Y Y Q E H D Q K A E S C D F G G L G L I T T V D P S D D R C R F P I E I H T S N V E L Y R V C S F
 I I R S M I R H L K V A T L G G L D * S Q L L I R Q M I V A G F R L R F T L L M * H F T T G C U V F
 L L S G A * S E S * K L R L W G A W I N H H C * S V R * S L Q V S D * D S H F * C R T L Q G V * F S

GCTGAAACTTGGCAGCTTTGGGGGGCTTGGGATTAATCACAACCTGTTGATCCGTCAGATGATCCGTCAGGTTCCGATGGAG
 H S Y Y Q E H D Q K A E S C D F G G L G L I T T V D P S D D R C R F P I E I H T S N V E L Y R V C S F Q
 * L L S G A * S E S * K L R L W G A W I N H H C * S V R * S L Q
 L I V I R S M I R H L K V A T L G G L D * S Q L L I R Q M I V A G F R L R F T L L M * H F T T G C U V F
 * L L S G A * S E S * K L R L W G A W I N H H C * S V R * S L Q

GCTGAAACTTGGCAGCTTTGGGGGGCTTGGGATTAATCACAACCTGTTGATCCGTCAGATGATCCGTCAGGTTCCGATGGAG
 S H G L V I Y H M L F H S Y Y Q E H D Q K A E S C D F G G L G L I T T V D P S D D R C R F P I E I H
 H M A * * Y I I C F L I V I R S M I R H L K V A T L G G L D * S Q L L I R Q M I V A G F R L R F
 T W P S N I S Y A F * * L L S G A * S E S * K L R L W G A W I N H H C * S V R * S L Q V S D * D S

GCTGAAACTTGGCAGCTTTGGGGGGCTTGGGATTAATCACAACCTGTTGATCCGTCAGATGATCCGTCAGGTTCCGATGGAG
 Y Y Q E H D Q K A E S C D F G G L G L I T T V D P S D D R C R F P I E I H T S N V E L Y R V C S F Q
 I I R S M I R H L K V A T L G G L D * S Q L L I R Q M I V A G F R L R F T L L M * H F T T G C U V F
 L S G A * S E S * K L R L W G A W I N H H C * S V R * S L Q V S D * D S H F * C R T L Q G V * F S

GCTGAAACTTGGCAGCTTTGGGGGGCTTGGGATTAATCACAACCTGTTGATCCGTCAGATGATCCGTCAGGTTCCGATGGAG
 Y Q E H D Q K A E S C D F G G L G L I T T V D P S D D R C R F P I E I H T S N V E L Y R V C S F Q

CP73, petioles under drought:
MtrunA17_Chr4g0034271, primary source
roots polyA

Consensus
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

Identity
REV 1. 2229621749_SRR949254.1700555
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

FIND 2. MtrunA17_Chr4g0034271 cDNA
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

CP74, flowers:

MtrunA17_Chr4g0034491, primary source

shoot apical buds (1, 2)

Consensus

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

Identity

1. 1 250546722_SRR11637999.14863466

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

2. 2 250555558_SRR11637999.14872302

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

3. MtrunA17_Chr4g0034491 cDNA

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

File
Align
CP92, roots, stems:

MtrunA17_Chr5g0431401, primary source

14-dpi nodules (1, 2)

File
Align

CP94, flowers:

MtrunA17_Chr5g0444231, primary source

petioles (1), 10-dpi nodules (3), 14-dpi nodules (2)

Consensus

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

Identity

FWO 1. 1 589588053_SRR15439239.8397368

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

REV 2. 2 1061366274_SRR5740862.12691901

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

REV 3. 3 1167603309_SRR5740864.5965569

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

FWO 4. MtrunA17_Chr5g0444231 cDNA

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

660 670 680 690 700 710 720 730 735 740 750 760 770 780 790 799 800

TTAGACGAGCTTAGTTAAGTGTACAGAGAAATCGGAGGTGTTGGACTTACAATACATGAAGAGCTCCTTGGGCAGGAAAAGATTCTAGATGAACTGGGAAATGAGATGGACAGTACATCCAATCGTTTAGATTTTGTCAAAAAAAGAGTGGCAATGCG
 * T S L V * V Y R E S E V L D L Q Y M K S S L G R K R F * M N W E M R W T V H P I V * I L S K K E W Q W
 V R R A * F K C T E N R R C W T Y N T * R A P W A G K K D S R * T G K * D G Q Y I Q S F R F C Q K K K S G N G
 L D E L S L S V Q R I G G V G L T I H E E L L G Q E K I L D E L G N E M D S T S N R L D F V Q K R V A M

GACGAGCTTAGTTAAGTGTACAGAGAAATCGGAGGTGTTGGACTTACAATACATGAAGAGCTCCTTGGGCAGGAAAAGATTCTAGATGAACTGGGAAATGAGATGGACAGTACATCCAATCGTTTAGATTTTGTCAAAAAAAGAGTGGCA
 T S L V * V Y R E S E V L D L Q Y M K S S L G R K R D F * M N W E M R W T V H P I V * I L S K K E W
 R A * F K C T E N R R C W T Y N T * R A P W A G K K I L D E L G N E M D S T S N R L D F V Q K K R S V A
 D E L S L S V Q R I G G V G L T I H E E L L G Q E K

TTAGCAATACATGAAGAGCTCCTTGGGCAGGAAAAGATTCTAGATGAACTGGGAAATGAGATGGACAGTACATCCAATCGTTTAGATTTTGTCAAAAAAAGAGTGGCA
 L Q Y M K S S L G R K R D F * M N W E M R W T V H P I V * I L S K K
 Y N T * R A P W A G K K I S R * T G K * D G Q Y I Q S F R F C Q K K
 T I H E E L L G Q E K I L D E L G N E M D S T S N R L D F V Q K K

AATACATGAAGAGCTCCTTGGGCAGGAAAAGATTCTAGATGAACTGGGAAATGAGATGGACAGTACATCCAATCGTTTAGATTTTGTCAAAAAAAGAGTGG
 Y M K S S L G R K R D F * M N W E M R W T V H P I V * I L S K K
 N T H E R E A P W A G K K I S R * T G K * D G Q Y I Q S F R F C Q K K R S
 I H E E L L G Q E K I L D E L G N E M D S T S N R L D F V Q K R V

TTAGACGAGCTTAGTTAAGTGTACAGAGAAATCGGAGGTGTTGGACTTACAATACATGAAGAGCTCCTTGGGCAGGAAAAGATTCTAGATGAACTGGGAAATGAGATGGACAGTACATCCAATCGTTTAGATTTTGTCAAAAAAAGAGTGGCAATGCG
 * T S L V * V Y R E S E V L D L Q Y M K S S L G R K R D F * M N W E M R W T V H P I V * I L S K K E W Q W
 V R R A * F K C T E N R R C W T Y N T * R A P W A G K K I L D E L G N E M D S T S N R L D F V Q K R S G N G
 L D E L S L S V Q R I G G V G L T I H E E L L G Q E K I L D E L G N E M D S T S N R L D F V Q K R V A M

CP98, buds:

MtrunA17_Chr6g0457471, alternative source

shoots

Consensus

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

Identity

REV 1. 762684598_SRR18944067.11692143

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

FWD 2. MtrunA17_Chr6g0457471

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

CP100, buds, whole plants, petioles, petioles under drought:

MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461, primary source

seedlings (1, 2)

Consensus

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

Identity

REV 1. 1 7532585_SRR10058814.7532585

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

FWD 2. 2 71543237_SRR10058822.11196958

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

FWD 3. MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461 cDNA

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

File

Align

CP110, seeds:

MtrunA17_Chr7g0214741, primary source

shoots (1), 10-dpi nodules (2)

Consensus
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

Identity

- ▶ REV 1. 1 774896912_SRR18944067.23904457
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
- ▶ REV 2. 2 1377587500_SRR5740870.12408168
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
- ▶ FWD 3. MtrunA17_Chr7g0214741 cDNA
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

CP123, seeds:

Zoom-in view, MtrunA17_Chr8g0380331, alternative source

seedlings (1), shoot apical buds (2)

Consensus
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

170 180 190 200 210 220 230 240 250 260 270 280 290 300 310 320

I T C C G G C C A A G A C G T C C G C A C T C A A A A C G T G G T A G C A T G T C A A G C C G T C G C G A A C A T C G T G A A A A A C C T C A C T C G G T C C C G T T G G T C T C G A C A A G A G G C T T G T T G A T G A T A T C G G T G A R G T G A C T A T T A C T A A T G A T G G T G C T A C T A T A C T T A A G A T G

I S R P R R R P H S K R G V S M S S R R E H R V E N L T R S R W S R Q E A C * * Y R * G / C D Y Y * * W C Y Y T * D

I P A K T S A L K T W * H V K P S R T S * K T P H S V P L V S T R G L V D D I G E / D V T I T N D G A T I L K M C

Identity

1. 1 10865540_SRR10058814.3103348

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

C G A A C A T C G T G A A A A C C T C A C T C G G T C C C G T T G G T C T C G A C A A G A G G C T T G T T G A T G A T A T C G G T G A G G T G A C T A T T A C T A A T G A T G G T G C T A C T A T A C T T A A G A T G

E H R E N L T R S R W S R Q E A C * * Y R * G D Y Y * * W C Y Y T * D

R T S * K T P H S V P L V S T R G L V D D I G E V T I T N D G A T I L K M C

2. 2 135605404_SRR11637997.20290913

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

I T C C G G C C A A G A C G T C C G C A C T C A A A A C G T G G T A G C A T G T C A A G C C G T C G C G A A C A T C G T G A A A A C C T C A C T C G G T C C C G T T G G T C T C G A C A A G A G G C T T G

I S R P R R R P H S K R G V S M S S R R E H R V E N L T R S R W S R Q E A

I P A K T S A L K T W * H V K P S R T S * K T P H S V P L V S T R G L

3. MtrunA17_Chr8g0380331 cDNA

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

I T C C G G C C A A G A C G T C C G C A C T C A A A A C G T G G T A G C A T G T C A A G C C G T C G C G A A C A T C G T G A A A A C C T C A C T C G G T C C C G T T G G T C T C G A C A A G A G G C T T G

I S R P R R R P H S K R G V S M S S R R E H R V E N L T R S R W S R Q D A C * * Y R * C D Y Y * * W C Y Y T * D

I P A K T S A L K T W * H V K P S R T S * K T P H S V P L V S T R M L V D D I G D V T I T N D G A T I L K M C

CP140, petioles under drought:

Group 1, overview, MtrunA17_Chr8g0392351, primary source

14-dpi nodules (7, 8, 9, 12, 13, 27), mature leaves (1, 2, 3, 4), nodules ribo-minus (14, 16, 19, 25), roots ribo-minus ([16], 18, [19], 20, 21, [25]), roots (5)

- 8. 9 704661109_SRR18299115.15202048
 - Frame 1
 - Frame 2
 - Frame 3
- 9. 12 729822866_SRR18299116.4692477
 - Frame 1
 - Frame 2
 - Frame 3
- 10. 13 694824824_SRR18299115.5365763
 - Frame 1
 - Frame 2
 - Frame 3
- 11. 14 2022698552_SRR949251.61623480
 - Frame 1
 - Frame 2
 - Frame 3
- 12. 16 2141079679_SRR949252.49038935
 - Frame 1
 - Frame 2
 - Frame 3
- 13. 18 2703109135_SRR949259.4414861
 - Frame 1
 - Frame 2
 - Frame 3
- 14. 19 2125203030_SRR949252.33162286
 - Frame 1
 - Frame 2
 - Frame 3
- 15. 20 2583977170_SRR949258.9539217
 - Frame 1
 - Frame 2
 - Frame 3
- 16. 21 2579421938_SRR949258.4983985
 - Frame 1
 - Frame 2
 - Frame 3
- 17. 25 2169625926_SRR949253.4871144
 - Frame 1
 - Frame 2
 - Frame 3
- 18. 27 665182610_SRR18299114.18333681
 - Frame 1
 - Frame 2
 - Frame 3
- 19. MtrunA17_Chr8g0392351 cDNA
 - Frame 1
 - Frame 2
 - Frame 3

The image displays a multiple sequence alignment of CP140 protein variants. The alignment is presented in three frames (Frame 1, Frame 2, Frame 3) for each sample. Conserved regions are highlighted in various colors: cyan, yellow, green, and red. The alignment shows high sequence identity across the different samples, particularly in the regions highlighted. At the bottom of the alignment, a protein domain diagram is shown with a red arrow indicating the direction of the protein sequence and a blue arrow indicating a specific domain or region. The diagram is labeled with '1' and '2'.

CP140, petioles under drought: Group 1, MtrunA17_Chr8g0392351, primary source

Extract R.C. Translate Add Annotation Allow Editing Annotate & Predict Primer Design Save

Consensus
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

Identity

- 7. 8 732502732_SRR18299116.7372343
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3
- 8. 9 704661109_SRR18299115.15202048
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3
- 9. 12 729822866_SRR18299116.4692477
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3
- 10. 13 694824824_SRR18299115.5365763
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3
- 11. 14 2022698552_SRR949251.61623480
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3
- 12. 16 2141079679_SRR949252.49038935
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3
- 13. 18 2703109135_SRR949259.4414861
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3
- 14. 19 2125203030_SRR949252.33162286
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3
- 15. 20 2583977170_SRR949258.9539217
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3
- 16. 21 2579421938_SRR949258.4983985
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3
- 17. 25 2169625926_SRR949253.4871144
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3
- 18. 27 665182610_SRR18299114.18333681
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3
- 19. MtrunA17_Chr8g0392351 cDNA
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

Genomic map at the bottom shows exons as red arrows and introns as blue lines. Exons are labeled 1 and 2. A zoomed-in view of a region is shown in a separate window at the bottom.

File
Align

CP140, petioles under drought:

Group 3, MtrunA17_Chr8g0392351, primary source

nodules ribo-minus (29, 31), roots ribo-minus (30)

Consensus

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

Identity

- 1. 29 2002498639_SRR949251.41423567
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
- 2. 30 2592829448_SRR949258.18391495
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
- 3. 31 2172765264_SRR949253.8010482
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
- 4. MtrunA17_Chr8g0392351 cDNA
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

CP140, petioles under drought:

Group 4, MtrunA17_Ch8g0392351, primary source

14-dpi nodules (6, 10)

Consensus
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

Identity

REV 1. 6 642516721_SRR18299114.16978440
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

FWD 2. 10 660154506_SRR18299114.13305577
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

FWD 3. MtrunA17_Ch8g0392351 cDNA
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

File
Align
←

CP140, petioles under drought:

Group 5, MtrunA17_Chr8g0392351, primary source

14-dpi nodules (17)

Consensus
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

Identity

1. 17.661652303_SRR18299114.14803374
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
2. MtrunA17_Chr8g0392351 cDNA
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

CP148, seeds:

Group 1, overview, MtrunA17_MTG0490471, primary source

14-dpi nodules (2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12, 14, 15, 17, 18, 20, 21, 26, 27, 29, 30, 45, 46, 47), mature leaves (13, 16, 22, 23, 24, 25), nodules ribo-minus (31, 32, 34, 36, 38, 39, 44), roots ribo-minus ([31], [32], [34], 35, [36], 42), seedlings (10)

- REV 2. 2 684467514_SRR18299115.16307937
- REV 3. 3 717427422_SRR18299116.6668877
- REV 4. 4 672549557_SRR18299115.4389980
- FUD 5. 5 662999987_SRR18299114.16151058
- REV 6. 6 627019689_SRR18299114.1481408
- FUD 7. 7 694701027_SRR18299115.5241966
- REV 8. 8 671580477_SRR18299115.3420900
- REV 9. 9 670757520_SRR18299115.2597943
- REV 10. 10 4474274_SRR10058814.4474274
- REV 11. 11 627019615_SRR18299114.1481334
- REV 12. 12 710829265_SRR18299116.70720
- REV 13. 13 1570033391_SRR7589436.49145775
- REV 14. 14 639413752_SRR18299114.13875471
- REV 15. 15 628543459_SRR18299114.3005178
- REV 16. 16 1527218248_SRR7589436.6330632

File

CP148, seeds:

Group 1, Part 1, MtrunA17_MTg0490471, primary source

Consensus
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

Identity

▶ FID 1. MtrunA17_MTg0490471 cDNA
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

▶ REV 2. 2.684467514_SRR18299115.16307937
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

▶ REV 3. 3.717427242_SRR18299116.6668877
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

▶ REV 4. 4.672549557_SRR18299115.4389980
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

▶ FID 5. 5.662999987_SRR18299114.16151058
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

▶ REV 6. 6.627019689_SRR18299114.1481408
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

▶ FID 7. 7.694701027_SRR18299115.5241966
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

▶ REV 8. 8.671580477_SRR18299115.3420900
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

▶ REV 9. 9.670757520_SRR18299115.2597943
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

▶ REV 10. 10.4474274_SRR10058814.4474274
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

▶ REV 11. 11.627019615_SRR18299114.1481334
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

▶ REV 12. 12.710829265_SRR18299116.70720
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

▶ REV 13. 13.157003391_SRR7589436.49145775
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

▶ REV 14. 14.639413752_SRR18299114.13875471
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

▶ REV 15. 15.628543459_SRR18299114.3005178
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

▶ REV 16. 16.1527218248_SRR7589436.6330632
 Frame 1

File

CP148, seeds:

Group 1, Part 3, MtrunA17_MTg0490471, primary source

Consensus
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

Identity

REV 23. 24 1506354708_SRR7589436.45467152
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 24. 25 1530896636_SRR7589436.10009020
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

FIND 25. 26 659079479_SRR18299114.12230550
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 26. 27 687539272_SRR18299115.19379695
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 27. 29 680619934_SRR18299115.12460357
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 28. 30 720229333_SRR18299116.9470788
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 29. 31 2086482876_SRR949252.44225471
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

FIND 30. 32 2009954737_SRR949251.48879665
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 31. 34 1952227152_SRR949251.72334413
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 32. 35 2630882127_SRR949259.26446804
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 33. 38 2089115080_SRR949252.46857675
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

FIND 34. 39 2019230945_SRR949251.58155873
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 35. 42 2560752811_SRR949258.16312228
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 36. 44 2161748460_SRR949253.19924377
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 37. 45 720155711_SRR18299116.9397166
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 38. 46 685062218_SRR18299115.16902641
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

REV 39. 47 678666877_SRR18299115.10507300
 Frame 1
 Frame 2
 Frame 3

Consensus sequence: **ATGCTTAAATAATCGATTCTGGH-AGCAGCCACCCCTGCGATCCGCACTCCGCAATATCGCCCAATCTCGGGGCG-CCATGGGGGAAATATCCCG**

Reference sequence 1: **GAATAAGGAATGCACGCATTAATAATCTATGATGATCTTAGTAAACGGG**

Reference sequence 2: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 3: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 4: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 5: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 6: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 7: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 8: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 9: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 10: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 11: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 12: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 13: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 14: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 15: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 16: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 17: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 18: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 19: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 20: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 21: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 22: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 23: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 24: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 25: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 26: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 27: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 28: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 29: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 30: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 31: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 32: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 33: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 34: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 35: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 36: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 37: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 38: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 39: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 40: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 41: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 42: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 43: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 44: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 45: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 46: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 47: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 48: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 49: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

Reference sequence 50: **CGGGGCAATCGCAAAAGCGATATGCTTAGCCGACCCACGGCCGCGAGCCGTTCCAGGGCGAGT**

CP148, seeds:

Group 2, MtrunA17_MTg0490471, primary source

nodules ribo-minus (33, 36, 40, 43), 14-dpi nodules (1), roots ribo-minus (41), mature leaves (19)

- Consensus
- Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
- Identity
- 1. 1 647045382_SRR1829114.196453
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
 - 2. 19 1652740875_SRR7589436.16146003
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
 - 3. 33 2134765075_SRR949252.42724331
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
 - 4. 36 2104682780_SRR949252.12642036
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
 - 5. 40 1995185739_SRR949251.34110667
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
 - 6. 41 2595844524_SRR949258.21406571
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
 - 7. 43 2184154582_SRR949253.19399800
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3
 - 8. MtrunA17_MTg0490471 cDNA
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

950 960 970 980 990 1,000 1,006 1,010 1,020 1,030 1,040 1,050 1,054 1,060 1,070 1,080 1,090

GGATCCCTGCACCTCTGCAATTTCTGGCCCCAATTTCTGGGTGTCGCATGGGGGAATAATTCGGCGATAAATGGAAATGCACGCATTAATAAATCTATGATGATCTTAGTAAAAGATGGGAAGAGCGTCGTGAGGGAAAGAGTGTAGATCTCGGTGG

D P A P L Q F L A P Y S G C A M G E Y F R A D N G M H A L I I Y D D L S K R S E E R R E V ? ? ? ? ? ? ? ? R ? P ?

R I L H L C N F W P H I F L G V C P W G N I F S P A I M E C T H * * S M M I L V K D R K S V V K / * ? ? ? ? ? D / Y ? D / G ? Q

G S C T S A I S G P I F W V C H G G I F P R * W N A R I N N L * * S * * K I G R A S * / C ? ? ? ? ? ? ? ? P / S ? T / A R

CCCTGCACCTCTGCAATTTCTGGCCCCAATTTCTGGGTGTCGCATGGGGGAATAATTCGGCGATAAATGGAAATGCACGCATTAATAAATCTATGATGATCTTAGTAAAAGATGGGAAGAGCGTCGTGAGGGAAAGAGTGTAGATCTCGGTGG

P A P L Q F L A P Y S G C A M G E Y F R A D N G M H A L I I Y D D L S K R S E E R R R V G K E C R S R W

L H L C N F W P H I F L G V C P W G N I F S P A I M E C T H * * S M M I L V K D R K S V * G K S V D L G

C T S A I S G P I F W V C H G G I F P R * W N A R I N N L * * S * * K I G R A S C R E R V * I S V

CCCAATTTCTGGGTGTCGCATGGGGGAATAATTCGGCGATAAATGGAAATGCACGCATTAATAAATCTATGATGATCTTAGTAAAAGATGGGAAGAGCGTCGTG

P Y S G C A M G E Y F R A D N G M H A L I I Y D D L S K R S E E R R V

H I L H L C N F W P H I F L G V C P W G N I F S P A I M E C T H * * S M M I L V K D R K S V R V

P I F W V C H G G I F P R * W N A R I N N L * * S * * K I G R A S

CGGATAAATGGAAATGCACGCATTAATAAATCTATGATGATCTTAGTAAAAGA

R D N G M H A L I I Y D D L S K R

A I M E C T H * * S M M I L V K R

R * W N A R I N N L * * S * * K I

CGGATAAATGGAAATGCACGCATTAATAAATCTATGATGATCTTAGTAAAAGAT

D N G M H A L I I Y D D L S K R

A I M E C T H * * S M M I L V K D

R * W N A R I N N L * * S * * K I

CGATAAATGGAAATGCACGCATTAATAAATCTATGATGATCTTAGTAAAAGAT

D N G M H A L I I Y D D L S K R

I M E C T H * * S M M I L V K D

R * W N A R I N N L * * S * * K I

CGGATAAATGGAAATGCACGCATTAATAAATCTATGATGATCTTAGTAAAAGA

D N G M H A L I I Y D D L S K R

A I M E C T H * * S M M I L V K R

R * W N A R I N N L * * S * * K I

GATAAATGGAAATGCACGCATTAATAAATCTATGATGATCTTAGTAAAAGAT

D N G M H A L I I Y D D L S K R

A V A Y I R Q M S L L L R R P P

R I L H L C N F W P H I F L G V C P W G N I F S P A I M E C T H * * S M M I L V K R A P W A Y I R Q M S L L L R R P P

G S C T S A I S G P I F W V C H G G I F P R * W N A R I N N L * * S * * T G R G I S T K N V I I V T P T T R

CP148, seeds:

Group 3, MtrunA17_MTg0490471, primary source

14-dpi nodules (28)

Consensus

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

Identity

1. 28 691305083_SRR18299115.1846022

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

2. MtrunA17_MTg0490471 cDNA

Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

File
Align

CP148, seeds:

Group 4, MtrunA17_MTg0490471, primary source

nodules ribo-minus (37)

Consensus
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

Identity

REV 1. 37 2089942742_SRR949252.47685337
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

FWD 2. MtrunA17_MTg0490471 cDNA
Frame 1
Frame 2
Frame 3

File
Align
CP149, 10-dpi nodules, 14-dpi nodules, flowers, leaves, seeds:
MtrunA17_MTg0490471, primary source
14-dpi nodules (37)

Consensus

400 409 420 430 440 450 460 470 478 480 490 500 510 520 530 540 550 560

GGTGTGAAA GG AATAGCGTTGAATCTTGAGAA TGAGAA TGTGGAA TGTGTTCTTTGGTAGTGATACCTCTATCAAAG AAGGAGATCTTGTCAAACGTA CTGGATCTATTGTGGTGTCTTCTGGGGCAAGGCTATGCTGGGGCCTGTTGGTGGTGGGAGT

G V K G I A L N L E N E N V G I V V F G S D T ? I K E G D L V K R T G S I V D A V P A G K A M L G P R V V D A A L G G V

A V * K E * R * I L R M R M S E L L S L V V I P L S K K E I L S N V L D L L W M L F L R E A R L C * S G L V W S T P P R W G E V

R C E R N S V E S * E * E C R N C C L W * * Y ? Y Q R R R S C Q T Y W I Y C G C S C G K Q G Y A R A C G R R V G S

Identity

- 1. 694598064_SRR18299115.5139003
- 2. MtrunA17_MTg0490471 cDNA

AA GG AATAGCGTTGAATCTTGAGAA TGAGAA TGTGGAA TGTGTTCTTTGGTAGTGATACCTCTATCAAAG AAGGAGATCTTGTCAAACGTA CTGGATCTATTGTGGTGTCTTCTGGGGCAAGGCTATGCTGGGGCCTGTTGGTGGTGGGAGT

K E I L S N V L D L L W L F L R A R L C S G L W S P K E I L S N V L D L L W L F L R A R L C S G L W S P

R N S V E S * E * E C R N C C L W * * Y -P I K E G D L V K R T G S I V A V P A G K A M L G P V V A

GGTGTGAAA GG AATAGCGTTGAATCTTGAGAA TGAGAA TGTGGAA TGTGTTCTTTGGTAGTGATACCTCTATCAAAG AAGGAGATCTTGTCAAACGTA CTGGATCTATTGTGGTGTCTTCTGGGGCAAGGCTATGCTGGGGCCTGTTGGTGGTGGGAGT

G V K G I A L N L E N E N V G I V V F G S D T S I K E G D L V K R T G S I V D V P A G K A M L G R V V D A L G V

A V * K E * R * I L R M R M S E L L S L V V I P L S K K E I L S N V L D L L W M L F L R E R L C * G V W S T A R L W E V

R C E R N S V E S * E * E C R N C C L W * * Y L Y Q R R R S C Q T Y W I Y C G C S C G K G Y A R A C G R R V G S

Supplementary Dataset S19. A graphical summary on alignments between transcripts of 15 MS-supported chimeric peptides and RNA-Seq reads from 50 selected RNA-Seq runs. RNA-Seq runs with names shown in blue match MS proteomic samples shown in the first line. Run names shown in red do not match corresponding MS samples. Run names shown in brown have partial match, for example, “10-dpi nodules” and “14-dpi nodules ”. Numbers between round brackets indicate read sequences that match a corresponding transcript. Numbers shown in square brackets indicate read sequences that are found in more than one run. For example, read 9 of CP54 is primarily found in a run from 14-dpi nodules. However, an identical sequence with a different ID is found also in a run from 10-dpi nodules. In each alignment, bases corresponding to the longer side of a chimeric peptide are annotated with cyan whereas bases of the shorter side are marked with purple. The PRF sites are annotated with deep purple. RefORFs and altORFs are labeled with yellow and pink, respectively. Each read number and ID along with the transcript ID are shown in alignment images. Screenshots are from Geneious® v. 7.1 (Dotmatics Ltd., MA, USA, <https://www.geneious.com>).